

The Major Effects and Challenges of Child Trafficking in India

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Abstract

Child trafficking is a serious problem that is prevalent especially in India. According to a report published by the U.S. Department of State, “India is a source, destination and transit country for men, women and children subjected to forced labour and sex trafficking. The majority of India’s trafficking problem is internal, and those from the most disadvantaged social strata- lowest caste Dalits, members of tribal communities, religious minorities and women and girls from excluded groups – are most vulnerable. These papers discuss about the major effects and challenges of the child trafficking in India. It includes physical, and mental health of the children and also its concludes with the necessity of social work implications to combat the modern slavery of the child trafficking.

Introduction

Trafficking of children is a worldwide phenomenon affecting large numbers of boys and girls every day. Children and their families are often lured by the promise of better employment and a more prosperous life far from their homes. Others are kidnapped and sold. Trafficking violates a child’s right to grow up in a family environment and exposes him or her to a range of dangers, including violence and sexual abuse. In India too, over the last decade, the volume of human trafficking has increased though the exact numbers are not known, it is one of the most lucrative criminal trades, next to arms and drug smuggling undertaken by highly organized criminals. Unless a public opinion is built laws are effectively designed and implemented, the situation is constantly monitored and the nexus of traffickers is exposed, Children will continue to be trafficked. Coordinated efforts are required to stop and prevent child trafficking.

History of Trafficking

Trafficking of human beings is not a new phenomenon. Historically, it has been linked to slavery which involved the sale and purchase of human beings as chattel, treating them as commodities that could be bought and sold. The owner maintained absolute rights over the slaves, who were considered his private property.

Child Trafficking: A Short Definition

A child has been trafficked if he or she has been moved within a country, or across borders, whether by force or not, with the purpose of exploiting the child.

Child Trafficking in India

India has a high volume of Child Trafficking. There have been many cases where children just disappear overnight, as many as one every eight minutes, according to the National Crime Records Bureau. In some cases, children are taken from their homes to be bought and sold in the market. In other cases, children are tricked into the hands of traffickers by being presented an opportunity for a job, when in reality, upon arrival they become enslaved. In India, there is a large number of children trafficked for various reasons such as labour, begging, and sexual exploitation.

The Major Reason Behind the Child Trafficking in India

The fact that children’s kidnapping has become the most serious problem in today’s environment is a widespread crime. There are many reasons behind in child trafficking

A root cause of commercial sexual exploitation and child trafficking in India is due to poverty, lack of education, and the need to support their family.

- To get out of poverty or debt, some parents have even sold their children to traffickers.
- Children are often trafficked by gangs and forced to beg on the streets.
- In some parts of India, young girls are forced into the system on Devadasi where they’re “forced into a lifetime of ritual sex slavery”
- A lot of children have also been trafficked due to the demand by tourists. People will travel from countries where there are strict enforcement’s around child trafficking, as well as it being heavily frowned upon and socially unaccepted, to India to find child prostitutes.

Statistics on Human Trafficking in India

On June 20 2014, John Kerry, the U.S. Secretary of State, made his inaugural speech on releasing the 2014 Trafficking in Persons Report (TIP).

According to the report, there are over 20 million persons trafficked for various forms of exploitation worldwide. It is estimated that the global business generated through direct and indirect human trafficking, is in the region of \$15.5 billion.

The report clearly refers to the existing situation of human exploitation and trafficking that involves men, women and children in India. India is a major point for sourcing, destination and trafficking of women and children as per the US Government’s 2014 TIP Report.

The problem is real and widespread.

- Over 90% of the trafficking is done within the borders and 10% is from overseas. The problem is spread over various forms of exploitation. Trafficking of women and young girls from Nepal and Bangladesh into India for sexual exploitation is the most common. These girls from poor families and often in the age group of 9-14 years are brought into India and sold to brothel owners in Kolkata, Mumbai and Delhi, amongst several other cities.
- A lot of young boys are trafficked into India for work as bonded labour in industries like coal, brick kilns, handloom and embroidery, rice mills and agriculture. They are made to work up to 16 hours a day in return for subsistence food and very little or no money. These children are often sexually exploited by their owners and beaten or tortured in cases of non-compliance.
- Several young boys from Bihar find their way to factories in Nepal, while young girls from Nepal are brought through transit points of Raxaul and Gorakhpur to be sold to traffickers in India. Kolkata is a major transit point and destination for girls and women coming from Nepal and Bangladesh.
- India is also a transit point for young boys who are sent to Dubai and other Middle-East countries for camel racing. Very often these young boys are sexually exploited and kept as bonded labourers.

- Another area where children are frequently sent to is Saudi Arabia, where begging is an organized billion dollar industry, especially during Haj. In India, begging syndicates often maim children and put them on to streets to get maximum collection from them.
- According to the National Human Rights Commission of India, over 40,000 children are reported missing every year of which over 11,000 remain untraced. It is in this backdrop, that the recent discovery of child trafficking into Kerala has got the government’s attention. Children from various states were being brought into Kerala by train.

Constitutional Legal Sections and Acts on the Prohibition of Child Trafficking

There are many Indian Penal Code sections and several legislations on the eradication of trafficking in persons are followed:

1. Procuration of minor girls (Section 366-A IPC)
2. Importation of girls from foreign country (Section 366-B IPC)
3. Selling of girls for prostitution (Section 372 IPC)
4. Immoral Trafficking (Prevention) Act, 1956
5. Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Act, 2000
7. Transplantation of Human Organs Act, 1994.

Recommended actions to be taken by the Government and Society. The TIP Report clearly mandates that all governments have to focus on:

- Prevention
- Prosecution
- Protection

The governments need to redefine laws to make them more stringent and ensure severe punishment delivered quickly. The Government must ensure that the necessary and effective infrastructure is in place to identify, arrest, prosecute all involved in the trafficking chain. Unless the entire chain feels the heat of the prosecuting agencies with active support from NGOs and Civil Society, our children will continue to be threatened by this social evil.

Conclusion

Trafficking in human beings, especially children, is a form of modern-day slavery and requires a holistic, multi-sectoral approach to address the complex dimension of the problem. In the fight against trafficking government organizations, non- governmental organizations, civil society, pressure groups, international bodies, all have to play an important role. Law cannot be the only instrument to take care of all problems.

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